

IMPROVING SCIENCE TEACHING EFFICIENCY
USING THE H5P PLUG

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Abstract: This work talks about the possibilities of improving the effectiveness of teaching computer science classes using the H5P plug-in. Interactivity and the use of technologies are of great importance in the modern educational process. The H5P plugin provides great opportunities in this regard. H5P (HTML5 Package) is an open source interactive content creation tool that can be integrated into various educational platforms. With H5P, teachers can easily create a variety of interactive elements, quizzes, presentations, and other learning materials.

Key words: Basic concepts: H5P(HTML5 Package), technology, practical training, Interactive training, plug-in.

The role of education in the life of modern society is mainly determined by the increasing role of knowledge and information, which is reflected in the concepts of information society, the formation of information civilization and the informatization of education. One of the most urgent tasks of the development of modern education in the context of innovative changes in society resulting from the widespread introduction of computer technologies is the implementation of global trends in the development of information and education in the information society. Thanks to the rapid development of computer technologies, people have access to various information, exchange information, and communicate in real time anywhere in the world. A modern specialist of any profile needs to receive, process and use information using computers, telecommunications and other means of communication in order to navigate freely in information flows. But for this you need to know the rules of navigation through the huge amount of information available and have a certain cultural culture.

The meaning of informatization of education is to create favorable conditions for teachers and students to freely use cultural, educational and scientific information. It is also important to understand that the informatization of the educational sphere should precede the informatization of other spheres of social activity, because it is here that there are social, psychological, general cultural and professional conditions for the development of a new social sphere.

type of society is established. Informatization and computerization are becoming objects of new learning, application and application in education, which allows to create a clear educational system.

Technologies are one of the aspects that are changing every sphere of our life, and they play an important role in bringing great changes in the educational process as well. There are now new approaches, various programs and plugins designed to facilitate the creation of interactive lessons and learning for students. H5P is one of the innovations in this field. Using the H5P plugin, you can increase the effectiveness of teaching computer science classes. This plugin allows teachers to create interactive and engaging lesson materials. Through interactive tests, videos, presentations and simulations, students are more actively involved in the learning process and help to better understand the educational material. The flexibility and easy integration capabilities of the H5P plugin allow it to be widely used in the educational process. Therefore, using the H5P plugin is an important tool for applying innovative and effective approaches in modern education.

The H5P plugin can be easily integrated into various educational platforms, including systems such as Moodle, WordPress, and Drupal. This allows teachers to integrate H5P content with existing learning resources and lessons. In addition, H5P content creation requires no technical knowledge, allowing teachers to create their own content quickly and easily. One of the main advantages of the H5P plugin is that it provides a high level of interactivity and is highly effective in increasing student learning and imagination. Teachers test students' understanding and increase learning by creating interactive quizzes. Also, animations and interactive infographics add to what readers see and understand. As a result, the importance of the H5P plugin in making the learning process more efficient and increasing is considered very high. With this plugin, teachers can create the following types of interactive elements:

Tests and Quizzes: A variety of tests and quizzes can be created to assess students' understanding of course material.

Interactive videos : Questions can be placed on different videos.

Figure 1.

Figure 2.

After the questions are placed on the videos, the reader will be faced with the questions while watching the video. If the questions are answered correctly, the video will continue, otherwise, if you go back, the video will start again from the beginning (Fig. 1-2).

Presentations and Slides: By creating presentations and slides enriched with various multimedia elements, the lesson can be made lively and interesting. The H5P plugin can be used to make cybersecurity lessons fun and effective:

Simulations and hands-on training: A variety of interactive simulations are available to teach different cyber security threats and how to mitigate them. This provides an opportunity for students to prepare for real-life situations.

Quizzes and Tests: Interactive quizzes and tests can be created to assess your cyber security knowledge. Through this, students can test their knowledge and identify their shortcomings.

In conclusion, the H5P plugin provides great opportunities for students to create interactive lessons and tests. With this plugin, teachers motivate students and facilitate their learning through interactive tests, animations, infographics and other interactive tools. As a result, students increase their learning and make the learning process more effective. The H5P plugin is an example of a more spiritual and augmented approach to teaching computer science classes.

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